

Pig Slurry Influence on Soil Physio-Chemical Properties in Ngor Okpala, Imo State, Nigeria

E. U. Uju, N. N. Oti, I. I. Ekpe, A. A. Isaiah

*Department of Soil Science Technology, Federal University of
Owerri, Nigeria*

Corresponding Author: Emmanuella Uchechi Uju,

e-mail: nuella1991@gmail.com

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Abstract

Recently, the importance of organic manure in enhancing soil physico-chemical properties cannot be overemphasized. Therefore a study was conducted to investigate pig slurry influence on soil physico-chemical properties in Ngor Okpala Imo State Nigeria. The experiment was laid out in a Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD) with five (5) treatments replicated four (4) times. Data obtained was analyzed using analysis of variance (ANOVA) and significant means were separated using Fisher least significant difference (F-LSD) at probability level of ($P=0.05$). The treatments consisted of P0-control. P1- pig slurry at 10 t ha^{-1} , P2- pig slurry at 20 t ha^{-1} , P3- pig slurry at 30 t ha^{-1} and P4- pig slurry at 40 t ha^{-1} . The result showed that application of pig slurry at 10 t ha^{-1} , 20 t ha^{-1} , 30 t ha^{-1} and 40 t ha^{-1} significantly ($P= 0.05$) improved the soil total porosity, moisture content and decreased the soil bulk density. Also the application of pig slurry at different rates improved the soil pH_w , organic carbon, total nitrogen, available phosphorous, exchangeable bases, Effective cation exchange capacity (ECEC) and percentage base saturation and significantly decreased the soil total exchangeable acidity. The trend of improving the soil physico-chemical properties was 40 t ha^{-1} , 30 t ha^{-1} , 20 t ha^{-1} , 10 t ha^{-1} and 0 t ha^{-1} . Therefore, it is recommended that farmers should use pig slurry in improving soil physico-chemical properties particularly at 40 t ha^{-1} rate of application.

Keywords: influence, chemical, physical, pig slurry, soil

Introduction

Soil nutrient management is necessary to maintain the constant productivity of crops as well as good quality soil. The application of manure in the soil improves its fertility and increases agricultural production (Yolanda *et al.*, 2016). The use of mineral fertilizer and organic manure to improve soil quality has both negative and positive effect on plant growth and soil (Si Ho Han *et al.*, 2016). Continuous use of mineral fertilizer for increasing soil nutrient is usually accompanied on the long term by reduction in soil organic matter, erosion, degradation of soil physical properties and decrease in soil pH (Cai *et al.*, 2015). Mineral fertilizer could also negatively impact the microbial diversity by altering the bacterial and fungal population (Asmita, 2019).

Organic manure on the other hand has shortcomings which include slow decomposition and low nutrient depending on the nutrient composition of the organic material (Si Ho Han *et al.*, 2016).

However, organic manure is considered less likely to have detrimental effects on soil physical and chemical properties compared with mineral fertilizer (Soremi *et al.*, 2017). Therefore, replacement of mineral fertilizer with organic manure can be an alternative to enhance soil quality and crop growth (Jiang *et al.*, 2018).

The application of organic manure to the soil has positive effect on soil physio-chemical properties mainly due to increase in organic matter (Yolanda *et al.*, 2014). The vital roles of organic matter include being a rich source of essential plant nutrients, helps in improving water holding capacity of soil, improves soil structure, soil aeration, water permeability, acts as pH buffer, contains metal organic matter complexes that help in making available micro nutrients to crops (Ikeh *et al.*, 2013, Soremi *et al.*, 2017).

Studies have shown that application of organic manure to the soil helps to increase soil quality and productivity by its own favorable effects on soil properties (Ozlu and Kumar, 2018). Ye *et al.*, (2019) also reported an increase in soil organic matter due to application of organic manure. Increase in soil organic matter can enhance aggregate stability; improve soil structure, increase nutrient cycling, microbial diversity and enzyme activity (Lupwayi *et al.*, 2019). Application of manure improve soil structure leading to high porosity, water holding capacity and water infiltration as well as maintains soil pH (Ozlu and Kumar, 2018). The availability of nutrients to crops is affected by the physio-chemical and biological properties of soil such as pH, organic matter, soil texture, nutrient interactions, soil moisture content, temperature and microbial activities Soremi *et al.*, 2017). Processes in the soil such as mineralization, humification, adsorption, desorption, precipitation, immobilization, leaching, diffusion and fixation could be triggered within the soil environment by the addition of organic manure which leads to changes in soil physio-chemical properties and resultant in optimum growth of crops. Therefore manure application is being promoted as an alternative to mineral fertilizer to enhance agricultural sustainability (Gai *et al.*, 2019).

The objective of this study was to investigate the influence of pig slurry on soil physio-chemical properties in Ngor Okpala Imo State Nigeria.

Materials and Methods

Site Description

The study was carried out at Umueme Obike in Ngor Okpala L.G.A, Imo State Nigeria. The study site is located on latitude $5^{\circ}18'50.352''\text{N}$ and Longitude $7^{\circ}8'34.062''\text{E}$. The study site had a humid tropical climate, annual temperature of $27-29^{\circ}$ and annual rainfall of 1500m-2500m which starts from March to December with its peak in July. The dry season starts from December to March with a dry dust and cold intervals. The vegetation consists of mostly grasses such as guinea grass (*Panicum maximum*), elephant grass (*Pennisetum purpureum*) and star grass (*Cynodon nlemfuensis*).

Site Preparation/Treatment Allocation

A total land area of 192m^2 (16×12) was used for the experiment. The experimental site was manually cleared using machetes, spade and hoe. Experimental plots were mapped out using Measuring tapes, pegs and ropes. Twenty (20) experimental plots were used for the study, measuring $2\text{m} \times 2\text{m}$ with 1m apart to separate the treatment effects from interfering with each other. The treatments comprised of P0- control, P1- Pig slurry at 10t ha^{-1} , P2- Pig slurry at 20t ha^{-1} , P3- Pig slurry at 30t ha^{-1} , P4- Pig slurry at 40t ha^{-1} .

Sourcing of Treatment Material

Pig slurry was sourced from Amici Ranch Integrated Farm Umueme Ngor Okpala, Imo State Nigeria.

Experimental Design

The experimental design used for the experiment was randomized complete block design (RCBD). The design consisted of five (5) treatments replicated four times as shown in figure 1.

Figure 1. Field layout of the Experimental Site

Soil Sampling

Soil samples were collected at 0-20 cm soil depth for soil physical and chemical properties using core samplers and soil Augar. The samples in the core samplers were used for the determination of soil physical properties. Samples collected were stored in polyethene bags and sent to the soil handling unit of FUTO laboratory for processing which include air drying, crushing and sieving using 2mm sieve in preparatory for routine analysis.

Laboratory Analysis

The laboratory soil analysis was carried out at Soil Science Laboratory of Federal University of Technology Owerri, Imo State and the following soil properties were determined; Organic

carbon was determined by the Walkley and Black (1934) wet-oxidation method as modified and described in manual of soil, plant and water analysis (Eno *et al.*, 2009) and the value for organic matter was obtained by multiplying organic carbon value by 1.724 (Van Bemmelen factor). Available phosphorous was determined by Bray and Kurtz No.2 (1945) method adopted by Juo (1979) in which the phosphorous was extracted with 1ml NH₄F and 0.5ml Hydrochloric acid. Colour development was achieved by adding “reagent B”. Available phosphorous was determined calorimetrically using a photoelectric calorimeter. Total nitrogen was determined by micro Kjeldahl digestion and distillation method of Bremner (1965) as recently modified and described in the manual of soil and water analysis (Eno *et al.*, 2009) using concentrated H₂SO₄ and a sodium copper sulphate catalyst mixture. Soil pH was determined in the laboratory with a glass pH meter at a ratio of 1:2.5 water ratios, exchangeable cations (Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺, Na⁺ and K⁺) were extracted with ammonium acetate solution, Exchangeable calcium and magnesium was determined by the ethylenediaminetetracetic acid titration method as described by Black (1965), whereas exchangeable potassium and sodium were determined by flame photometric method. Exchangeable acidity was determined by the titrimetric method described by Bray and Weit (1999). Total exchangeable acidity was determined by the summation of H⁺ and Al³⁺. Total exchangeable bases were determined by the summation of exchangeable cations (Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺, Na⁺ and K⁺). Effective Cation Exchange Capacity was determined by the summation of exchangeable acidity (Al³⁺ and H⁺) and exchangeable bases. Percentage base saturation (BS) was calculated by the summation of the total exchangeable bases (TEB) divided by effective cation exchange capacity (ECEC) and then multiplied by 100.

$$\% \text{ BS} = \frac{\text{TEB}}{\text{ECEC}} \times 1000 \quad \text{Equation}$$

(1)

The Selected Physical Properties determined were; Bulk density was determined using core method (Black and Hartge, 1986).

$$\text{Bulk Density} = \frac{\text{Weight of wet soil} - \text{Weight of dry soil}}{\text{Weight of wet soil}} \times 100 \quad \text{Equation}$$

(2)

Total porosity was calculated from the result of bulk density and particle size density. Total

$$\text{Porosity} = \frac{1 - \text{Bulk Density (g/cm}^3\text{)}}{\text{Particle Density}} \times 100 \quad \text{Equation (3)}$$

Particle Size Distribution was determined by hydrometric meter in water and Calgon (Bouyocous, 1951). Soil texture was determined by matching the value of the particle size against the textural triangle. Gravimetric moisture content will be determined by the gravimetric method calculated mathematically as follows:

$$\% \text{ MC} = \frac{W_2 - W_3}{W_3 - W_1} \times 100 \quad \text{Equation (4)}$$

Where MC = Moisture Content, W₁ = Weight of the core, W₂ = Weight of wet sample + core, W₃ = Weight of oven – dried sample + core.

Statistical Analysis

Data collected were analyzed using analysis of variance (ANOVA) with the aid of IBM SPSS statistics, version 23. The differences in mean were separated using Fishers Least Significant difference (FLSD) at $P = 0.05$.

Results and Discussion

Initial Soil Characteristics before Treatment Application

The initial physical and chemical properties of the soil before application of treatment are presented in Table 1

Table 1. Initial Soil Analysis

Soil Properties and Units of Measurement	Value
Physical properties	
Sand (%)	70.00
Silt (%)	42.40
Clay ((%)	22.20
Textural class	Loamy soil
Bulk Density (g cm^{-3})	1.51
Moisture Content (%)	7.02
Total Porosity (%)	37.9
Chemical properties	
pH in H_2O (1:2:5)	5.25
Organic Carbon (%)	1.35
Available phosphorous mg kg^{-1}	12.6
Total Nitrogen (%)	0.12
Calcium (Cmol kg^{-1})	1.40
Magnesium (Cmol kg^{-1})	0.31
Sodium (Cmol kg^{-1})	0.07
Potassium (Cmol kg^{-1})	0.05
Exchangeable acidity (Cmol kg^{-1})	1.39
Total Exchangeable Base (Cmol kg^{-1})	1.83
Effective Cation Exchange Capacity (Cmol kg^{-1})	3.22
Percentage Base Saturation (%)	56.83

The result on the analysis of the initial soil characteristics before pig slurry application on soil physical and chemical properties is shown in Table 1. The result showed that the soil of the experimental site is loamy soil, placing the values of sand, silt and clay on a textural triangle according to the United State Department of Agriculture (USDA). The bulk density recorded 1.51 g cm^{-3} which could be as a result of the anthropogenic activities being carried out on the site, although it was within the tolerable limit of 1.85 g cm^{-3} for plant growth (FAO 1996). The total porosity was high with value of 38.95%, this increase in total porosity could be as a result of the bulk density because the lower the bulk density the higher the soil porosity. The pH_w was slightly acidic (5.25) which is good for retaining plant nutrients. The soil organic carbon was low; the minimal threshold for soil organic carbon in tropical soils is 2% (Patrick *et al.*, 2013). Total nitrogen was low with

value of 0.12% and available phosphorous was moderate with value of 12.6 mg kg⁻¹. The result also recorded total exchangeable acidity (TEA) 1.39 Cmol kg⁻¹, total exchangeable bases (TEB) of 1.83 Cmol kg⁻¹, effective cation exchange capacity (ECEC) of 3.22 Cmol kg⁻¹ and percentage base saturation of 56.83%. Therefore these results indicated that the soil of the experimental site is low in soil fertility, hence will be improved by addition of organic input like pig slurry for optimum crop production.

Chemical Composition of Pig Slurry Used for the Experiment

The result on the chemical composition of pig slurry used in the experiment is shown in Table 2.

The result showed that the soil pH_w recorded 6.40 which is adequate for plant growth. The organic matter content was high with value of 28.2%. Total nitrogen and available phosphorous were high. The exchangeable bases calcium, magnesium, potassium and sodium were also high. This suggests that pig slurry is rich in mineral nutrients and would improve soil properties when added to the soil.

Table 2. *Chemical Composition of Pig Slurry Used for the Experiment*

Soil Parameters/Minerals	Values
pH in H ₂ O (1:2:5)	6.40
Organic Carbon (%)	16.4
Organic Matter (%)	28.2
Total Nitrogen (%)	6.80
Available phosphorous (mg kg ⁻¹)	10.60
Calcium (Cmol kg ⁻¹)	9.42
Magnesium (Cmol kg ⁻¹)	3.90
Potassium (Cmol kg ⁻¹)	5.21
Sodium (Cmol kg ⁻¹)	1.30

The Influence of Pig Slurry on Soil Physical Properties

The results of the influence of pig slurry on soil physical properties of the experimental site are shown in Table 3.

Particle size distribution

The result on pig slurry application on particle size distribution showed that there were no significant differences in % sand, % silt and % clay of the treated plots although there were variations in values. This could be attributed to the fact that the soil of the experimental site originated from the same parent material. The application of pig slurry at 10 t ha⁻¹ and 20 t ha⁻¹ increased in percentage sand, silt and clay content compared to the control. Also the application of pig slurry at 30 t ha⁻¹ reduced in % sand, silt and clay compared to P1 (10 t ha⁻¹) and P2 (20 t ha⁻¹). However, P4 (40 t ha⁻¹) recorded the highest % sand, silt and clay.

Bulk Density (g cm⁻³)

The Soil bulk density decreased with application of pig slurry. The different levels of pig slurry added to the soil recorded different significant (P=0.05) results. There was significant difference when the control was compared with the treatments and when the treatments were

different rates improved the soil moisture content from 6.98 – 8.57%. This improvement in soil moisture content with levels of pig slurry application is attributed to the mulching effect of organic manure and improved moisture retention and water acceptance as a result of improved soil structure and micro porosity (Adekiya *et al.*, 2016).

The Influence of Pig Slurry on Soil Chemical Properties

The results of the influence of pig slurry application on soil chemical properties of the experimental site are shown in Table 4.

Soil pH_w

Pig slurry influence on soil pH showed that there were significant ($P = 0.05$) difference when the control was compared with treatments at 10 t ha⁻¹, 20 t ha⁻¹, 30 t ha⁻¹, and 40 t ha⁻¹. The control decreased the pH of the soil with value of 0.84, 0.93, 1.12, and 1.66 compared with p1 (10 t ha⁻¹), p2 (20 t ha⁻¹), p3 (30 t ha⁻¹), and p4 (40 t ha⁻¹) respectively. Also when the treatments were compared with one another, Soil pH increased with an increasing rate of pig slurry application. 40 t ha⁻¹ rate improved the soil pH tremendously. There was a strong shift from acidity to slight acidic. The improvement in soil pH in the amended plots could be due to the liming effect of agro wasted as reported by Manna *et al.*, (2007). Also Soromi *et al.*, (2017) reported an increase in soil pH as a result of the release of basic cations by organic matter due to mineralization.

Organic Carbon

Pig slurry application significantly ($P = 0.05$) improved soil organic carbon when the control was compared with the treated plots at 10 t ha⁻¹, 20 t ha⁻¹, 30 t ha⁻¹, and 40 t ha⁻¹. Application of pig slurry increased soil organic carbon by 0.05, 0.38, 0.73 and 1.18% respectively. Also there was significant difference in soil organic carbon content of the treated plots. 10 t ha⁻¹ recorded 0.33, 0.68 and 1.13 less percentage organic carbon content compared to 20 t ha⁻¹, 30 t ha⁻¹, and 40 t ha⁻¹ rates. However the highest organic carbon content of the treated plots was achieved in pig slurry application at 40 t ha⁻¹. This increase in soil organic carbon content could be attributed to the release of organic carbon contained in pig slurry during mineralization. This is in line with the consistent findings of NRC (1996) who noted that applying animal manure increases the supply of organic carbon hence organic matter in the soil. Also the application of organic manure in general increases soil organic carbon (Ozlu and Kumar, 2018).

Total Nitrogen

The soil total nitrogen improved with pig slurry application at different rates compared with the control. There were also significant ($P = 0.05$) improvement in soil total nitrogen when the treatments were compared with one another. The control plot recorded 0.07, 0.08, 0.13 and 0.12% less total nitrogen compared with pig slurry treated plots at different rates respectively. Also there was an improvement in soil total nitrogen when the treated plots were compared with one another. The 10 t ha⁻¹ recorded 0.01, 0.06 and 0.17 less nitrogen compared with 20 t ha⁻¹, 30 t ha⁻¹ and 40 t ha⁻¹ treated plots respectively. The highest improvement was recorded in plots treated with 40 t ha⁻¹ followed by 30 t ha⁻¹ and 20 t ha⁻¹. This improvement in soil total nitrogen by application of pig slurry could be as a result of the mineralization of organic wastes such as pig slurry which resulted in the release of organic bound nutrients in the soil notably NPK and organic matter. (Ekpe *et al.*, 2017)

Table 4. Influence of Pig Slurry on Soil Chemical Properties

TRET	P ^H _w	OC (%)	N (%)	AVP (mg/kg)	Ca ²⁺	Mg ²⁺	K ⁺	Na ⁺	TEA	TEB	ECEC	BS %
					↑ Cmol/kg				↓ Cmol/kg			
P0	5.25 ^a	1.58 ^a	0.14 ^a	18.84 ^a	1.41 ^a	0.36 ^a	0.06 ^a	0.05 ^a	1.37 ^c	1.88 ^a	3.25 ^a	57.84 ^a
P1	6.09 ^b	1.63 ^b	0.21 ^c	23.69 ^c	1.67 ^b	0.58 ^b	0.08 ^a	0.08 ^b	1.32 ^d	2.41 ^b	3.73 ^b	64.61 ^b
P2	6.18 ^c	1.96 ^c	0.22 ^b	25.56 ^b	2.15 ^c	0.72 ^c	0.13 ^b	0.09 ^b	1.28 ^c	3.09 ^c	4.37 ^c	70.70 ^c
P3	6.37 ^d	2.31 ^d	0.27 ^d	29.76 ^d	2.22 ^d	0.77 ^d	0.18 ^c	0.13 ^c	1.24 ^b	3.30 ^d	4.54 ^d	72.68 ^d
P4	6.91 ^e	2.76 ^e	0.31 ^e	30.08 ^e	2.27 ^e	1.12 ^e	0.25 ^d	0.15 ^d	1.16 ^a	3.79 ^e	4.95 ^e	76.56 ^e
F-LSD (0.05)	0.0181	0.021	0.006	0.410	0.028	0.046	0.022	0.006	0.011	0.020	0.031	0.151

Key: OC = Organic Carbon, OM = Organic Matter, N = Nitrogen, AVP = Available Phosphorous, Ca = Calcium, Mg = Magnesium, K = Potassium, Na = Sodium, H = Hydrogen, AL = Aluminum, TEA = Total Exchangeable Acidity, TEB = Total Exchangeable Bases, ECEC = Effective Cation Exchange Capacity, BS = Base Saturation, P0 = Control, P1 = Pig Slurry at 10 t ha⁻¹, P2 = Pig Slurry at 20 t ha⁻¹, P3 = Pig Slurry at 30 t ha⁻¹, P4 = Pig Slurry at 40 t ha⁻¹.
Note: Figures with the same superscript are not statistically significant

Available Phosphorous

The influence of pig slurry on available phosphorous showed that the application of pig slurry at 10 t ha⁻¹, 20 t ha⁻¹, 30 t ha⁻¹, and 40 t ha⁻¹ significantly ($P = 0.05$) increased the phosphorous content of the soil compared to the control. The control plot recorded 4.85, 6.72, 10.92 and 11.24 less phosphorous content to 10 t ha⁻¹, 20 t ha⁻¹, 30 t ha⁻¹, and 40 t ha⁻¹ treated plots respectively. When the treatments at different rates were compared with one another, there were also significant ($P = 0.05$) differences observed. The 40 t ha⁻¹ rate improved the soil phosphorous content by 6.39, 4.52 and 0.32 compared with 10 t ha⁻¹, 20 t ha⁻¹ and 30 t ha⁻¹ treated plots respectively. However, the high content of available phosphorous at higher application rate of pig slurry application could be attributed to the effect of P content in pig slurry. Also the mineralization of organic P releases P into the soil solution contributing to the observed high available P content in the treated plots.

Total Exchangeable Bases (Ca, Mg, K, Na)

The total exchangeable bases of the soil improved with the application of pig slurry. The different rates of pig slurry application also recorded different significant ($P = 0.05$) results. There was significant difference when 10 t ha⁻¹ pig slurry applications was compared with 20 t ha⁻¹, 30 t ha⁻¹, and 40 t ha⁻¹. Also there was significant difference when 20 t ha⁻¹ was compared with 30 t ha⁻¹ and 40 t ha⁻¹. 30 t ha⁻¹ also differ significantly from 40 t ha⁻¹. Treatment rates of 10 t ha⁻¹, 20 t ha⁻¹, 30 t ha⁻¹, and 40 t ha⁻¹ recorded 0.53, 1.21, 1.42 and 1.91 Cmol kg⁻¹ more exchangeable bases compared with untreated plot (control). Also, 20 t ha⁻¹, 30 t ha⁻¹, and 40 t ha⁻¹ rates recorded 0.68, 0.89, and 1.38 Cmol kg⁻¹ higher exchangeable bases compared to 10 t ha⁻¹ rate. On the other hand, 40 t ha⁻¹ recorded 0.70 and 0.49 Cmol kg⁻¹ compared with 20 t ha⁻¹ and 30 t ha⁻¹, therefore 40 t ha⁻¹ recorded the highest increase in total exchangeable bases. The increased total exchangeable bases recorded by the treated plots could be due to the increased soil pH caused by the addition of pig slurry which invariably has a liming effect on the soil and this result is inline with the findings of Aruna *et al.*, (2020).

Total Exchangeable Acidity (TEA)

Pig slurry influence on total exchangeable acidity significantly reduced the acidity of the soil compared to the control. The treated plots (10 t ha⁻¹, 20 t ha⁻¹, 30 t ha⁻¹, and 40 t ha⁻¹) reduced the acidity of the soil by 0.05, 0.09, 0.13 and 0.21 Cmol kg⁻¹ respectively, when compared with control plot. Also when the treatments were compared with one another, significant differences were observed. The 40 t ha⁻¹ treated plot reduced the total exchangeable acidity significantly by 0.16, 0.12, 0.08 Cmol kg⁻¹ respectively when compared with 10 t ha⁻¹, 20 t ha⁻¹ and 30 t ha⁻¹ treated plots. However, the soil total exchangeable acidity decreased significantly with an increasing rate of pig slurry application. This decrease in total exchangeable acidity could be attributed to the increased total exchangeable bases. This result supports the findings of Edeh *et al.*, (2015) who noted a decrease in soil total exchangeable acidity due to the addition of organic waste.

Effective Cation Exchange Capacity (ECEC)

There was significant difference in soil ECEC when the control plot was compared with the treated plots. The control plot recorded significantly 0.48, 1.12, 1.29 and 1.70 Cmol kg^{-1} less ECEC compared with 10 t ha^{-1} , 20 t ha^{-1} , 30 t ha^{-1} , and 40 t ha^{-1} respectively. Also there was significant difference when the different treatment levels of pig slurry were compared with one another. 20 t ha^{-1} , 30 t ha^{-1} , and 40 t ha^{-1} recorded 0.64, 0.81 and 1.22 Cmol kg^{-1} more ECEC compared to 10 t ha^{-1} treated plot. 30 t ha^{-1} recorded 0.17 Cmol kg^{-1} over 20 t ha^{-1} and 40 t ha^{-1} recorded 0.41 Cmol kg^{-1} over 30 t ha^{-1} . The soil ECEC of the amended plots increased with an increasing rate of pig slurry application with the range 3.73-4.95 Cmol kg^{-1} . This indicates that organic matter retains nutrients by providing cation and anion exchange capacity. This supports the findings of NRC, (1996). Similar findings on the increase in soil ECEC was reported by Ojobor *et al.*, (2017).

Base Saturation (%)

There was significant difference in the soil % base saturation when the result of the control was compared with the results of the amended plots and when the treatments levels were compared with one another. The control recorded 6.77, 12.86, 14.84 and 18.72 % less base saturation compared to 10 t ha^{-1} , 20 t ha^{-1} , 30 t ha^{-1} and 40 t ha^{-1} respectively. Also 10 t ha^{-1} treated plot recorded 6.09, 8.07 and 11.95 % less base saturation compared to 20 t ha^{-1} , 30 t ha^{-1} , and 40 t ha^{-1} . The 30 t ha^{-1} treated plot recorded 1.98 and 3.88 less base saturation compared to 40 t ha^{-1} . However, there was superior improvement in soil percentage base saturation by the amended plots than the control plot with the highest increase in soil base saturation recorded in 40 t ha^{-1} treated plot. This improvement in the amended plots supports the findings of Saoussan *et al.*,(2020).

Conclusion

In this study, the results obtained had shown that pig slurry application at 10 t ha^{-1} , 20 t ha^{-1} , 30 t ha^{-1} and 40 t ha^{-1} improved soil physio-chemical properties and can be recommended as a good source of organic manure for improving soil properties. 40 t ha^{-1} was the best rate of application compared to 10 t ha^{-1} , 20 t ha^{-1} and 30 t ha^{-1} rates.

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